

Early Epigraphic Records of the Jains

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Mahavir attained nirvana in 527 BCE at the peak of his popularity, leaving behind a growing community of monks, nuns and followers as described in *Kalpa Sūtra*¹. His disciples spread his teachings beyond Magadha, patronized by the kings of northern India including the Nandas and their successors, the Mauryas. At the end of second century BCE, a large number of Jain monks and lay people migrated from Magadha to other parts of India. This was perhaps fearing persecution from the Suṅgas who came to power after the Mauryas. Then, in the Khārvela period (172 BCE²), Jains enjoyed patronage of king Khārvela in Kalinga. In Kuṣāna period of first and second century CE, Jain community flourished in Mathura³.

I have been interested in researching the earliest epigraphical evidence that mentions some of the important Jain terms. First, I wanted to find the earliest written mention of the Jains. Second was to identify earliest epigraphical evidence of Mahāvīra, and lastly, wanted to find the oldest written *Namokar Mantra*, the most important prayer of the Jains. This paper presents a summary of the research.

The Nigganthas :

Mauryan ruler Ashoka, 273-232 BCE, was a patron of the Buddhist doctrine, or *Dharma*. Ashoka's pillar edicts assert his desire to support spread of the *Dharma* throughout his kingdom. One of Ashoka's pillars is currently found in Feroz Shah Kotla in Delhi, India.

The pillar is installed on a three story pyramidal building, which was specially commissioned for this purpose by Feroz Shah, the ruler of Delhi Sultanate in 14th century AD. Feroz Shah had the pillar transported from Topra, a town near present day Ambala. This 13-meter tall monolithic pillar is made of polished sandstone and has inscriptions in Brahmi script.

Ashokan Topra pillar © Nirmal Baid

Ashoka's pillars have six edicts describing his governing principles inscribed on them. In addition to the six edicts, the Topra pillar also has a seventh edict. The peculiar seventh edict, which is only found on this pillar, is inscribed around the pillar. It specifies the practicalities by which Ashoka promoted the *Dharma*.

According to the seventh edict, Ashoka planted fruit trees, built water sheds and constructed rest houses along the high roads, to provide people the opportunity to practice Dharma. Ashoka appointed wisemen (*Mahāmātras*) to preach the Dharma. He also appointed Mahamatras to penetrate followers of major doctrines of the time – Brahmins, *Nigganthas* and Ajivikas.

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Inscriptions on the Topra pillar © Nirmal Baid

The line five of the seventh edict makes a mention of the Nigghanthas.

Line 5 of VII Ashokan Edict in Brahmi with the word Nigghantha in box⁴

A transliteration of this line in Roman script is as follows⁵:

ime viyāpatā hohantiti; niganthesu pime kate, ime viyāpatā hohantiti : nān pāsandesu pime kate, ime viyāpatā hohantiti: pativisitha pativisitham tesu tesu te te mahāmātā dhammā mahāmātā cha me eteṣu cheva viyāpatā, saveṣu cha anesu pāsandesu. Devānāmpiye Piyadasi lājā hevam āhā:

A partial translation of text in Line 4 and 5 roughly reads ⁶,

...those Dharma-Mahāmātras of mine are occupied with

various kinds of activities which are beneficial both to ascetics and to householders. ...Similarly I have arranged that some of them (Mahāmātras) to engage with the Nigghanthas ...

Buddhist scriptures refer to Jains as *Nigghanthas*. Jacobi first arrived at this conclusion, and that the person mentioned as *Nigghantha Nāputta* in the Buddhist texts is the same personage as Mahāvīra⁷.

According to the sixth pillar edict, Ashoka began to issue edicts in twelve years after his coronation making these edicts to be dated about 257BC⁸. This makes appearance of word *Nigghanthesu* in line five of the seventh Ashokan edict, the oldest written mention of the Jains. The term *Nigghanthesu* is used as a vocative plural, indicative of Jain monastics.

The Navakāra Mantra :

After the Mauryas, Jains continued to flourish into the second century BC, as evidenced by the existence of the Jain caves in Udayagiri and Khandagiri outside Bhuvneshwara in Odisha. These caves were excavated as monasteries for Jain monks. Two of these caves known as Hathigumpha or the Elephant cave are of importance to the Jain archeology as they bear important inscriptions on their walls.

Inscriptions inside the Hathigumpha caves. © manishjaishree.com

of the Kusanas Mathura became the most important city of northern India. In Mathura, a large prosperous Jain community existed during the first and second century of the common era. Most of the evidence for this comes from an archeological site known as Kaṅkali Tilā.

Many Jain relics were found at the Kankali Tila including one Jain stupa, two temples, and many Āyāgapatas (Image below¹⁷), or tablets of homage with inscriptions recording dedication to the Arhats. Some of these inscriptions bear dates between year 5 and year 98 of the Kusana era¹⁸. Since there is no agreement on the year in which the Kushan era started, these Mathura relics can only be approximated to be from first two centuries of the common era.

An Āyāgapata from the Kaṅkali Tilā, Mathura.¹⁷

It is also worth noting that in his report, Growse, who excavated the Kaṅkali Tilā, mentioned that the mound was also called Jaini Tila, though without any additional reference¹⁹.

Almost 90 Jain inscriptions have been found from the Mathura excavations. Many bear names of the Tīrthaṅkaras as well as references to terms like Jina, Arhat etc. Almost 13 of these mention Vardhamāna or Mahāvīra²⁰. From around first century these tablet and stone inscriptions begin with “Adorations to Arhat Vardhamāna” or “Adorations to Arhat Mahāvīra”.

Following are two images²¹ of inscriptions from Sculpted tone slabs, now located in Lucknow Museum, that mention name of Mahāvīra. Transliteration²⁰ and translations follows the images.

inscriptions on stone slab from Kaṅkali Tilā with mention of Mahāvīra²¹

*namo arahato mahāvīrasa mathuraka ... lavaadasa [sa] ... bhayaye ... va ... itaye [ayaagapato]*²².

*Adorations to the Arhat Mahāvīra. A tablet of homage (ayagapata the gift) of ...ita, wife of ..lavada(?), an inhabitant of Mathura*²².

Inscriptions on stone slab from Kaṅkali Tilā with mention of Vardhamāna²¹

*namo arahato vardhamānasya gotiputrasa pothaya-saka ... alavalsa... Kosikiye Simitraye aayagapato prati(thapito)*²³

Adorations to the Arhat Vardhamāna! A tablet of homage was set up by Sivamitra (of) the Kausika (family) (wife) of Gotiputra, a black serpent for the Pothayas and Sakas²³.

These first century CE inscriptions make the oldest written mention of Vardhamāna Mahāvīra, the 24th Tīrthaṅkar of Jains.

The Last Word :

The third century BCE mention of the Jains, the second century BCE cave writing of the Navakāra Mantra, and the first century CE mention of Mahāvīra, represent some of the oldest and most important extant epigraphical records of the Jains.

I highly relied on the epigraphical work, including the transliterations and translations from the last two centuries to substantiate this work,. However, I did not come across work that directly stated that these epigraphs were the oldest mention of the important Jain terms.

I feel this article will not be complete without a reference to the Bhadrabāhu inscription found at Chandragiri in Shravanabelgola. The inscriptions are dated to be no later than 400AD²⁵.

Bhadrabāhu inscriptions at Chandragiri in Shravanabelgola.²⁴

A partial translation of the Bhadrabāhu inscription is as below²⁶.

...after Mahāvīra, (the succession of disciples was) Gautama gaṇadhara, his personal disciple Lohārya, Jambu, Viṣṇu-deva, Aparājita, Govardhana, Bhadrabāhu, Viśākha, Proshthila, Kṣatrikarya, Jayanama, Siddhārtha, Dhritshena, Buddhila and other gurus. Bhadrabāhu... had acquired the essence of knowledge, having, by power of discovering the past, present and future, foretold in Ujjayini a period of twelve-year of famine. - the whole of Sangha, leaving the northern regions, took their way to the South (Dakṣiṇapatha)...

In conclusion, these epigraphs are important records of the Jain history as they represent the oldest mention of the Jains, Mahāvīra, the Navakāra Mantra, a listing of the lineage of disciples after Mahāvīra's nirvana as well as a record of the migration of Jains to the South.

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- 6: pp600. Princep didn't capture an "n" sound in the word Niganthesu in his Brahmi transliteration.
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